

Orientation everyday

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Now we want to view the situation in a starting car. The inertia acceleration $\vec{t}$ is opposite to the acceleration $\vec{b}$ of the car. The visual vertical $\vec{o}$ is the vector sum $\vec{g} + \vec{t}$ with $\vec{g}$ as earth's acceleration (acceleration of gravity). To start we can look at the following figure:

$\vec{k}$ shall be the head's position. The head and the body move during starting in the direction of the inertia force.

Now we view the car during braking. The head moves in the direction of the inertia force (see fig.):

It is interesting to look at a plane during starting and landing. The situation during starting is like in the following figure:

During landing we have the following situation:

The visual vertical shows in the direction of the total acceleration $\vec{b}_{ges}$, if all accelerations are constant or changes slowly. A pendulum always shows in the direction of $\vec{b}_{ges}$, if there are no strong electric fields nearby. We can use the pendulum to determine the direction of $\vec{b}_{ges}$ in the car and in the plane. To the result in the plane see figure:

During starting:

During landing:

Now we look at the roundabout:

m shall be the observer's mass and g the earth's acceleration. At rotation of the roundabout there are the gravitational force $K = mg$ and the centrifugal force Z . We recognize from the figure:

$$\tan \phi = \frac{Z}{K}$$

For the centrifugal force Z we have the formula:

$$Z = mr\omega^2 = \frac{mv^2}{r}$$

with the following quantities:

ω = angular acceleration of the roundabout

v = velocity of the roundabout

$r = R + l \cdot \sin \phi$ with the cord's length l and radius of the roundabout's disk R .

If we insert the gravitational force and the centrifugal force in the equation of $\tan \phi$ and take into consideration the expression of r , then we obtain:

$$\tan \phi = \frac{(R + l \cdot \sin \phi) \cdot \omega^2}{g}$$

This equation can be solved to ϕ , then we get a function $\phi(\omega)$. With solving to ω we get a function $\omega(\phi)$. We don't do both here. $\phi = \angle(\vec{K}, \vec{K} + \vec{Z})$ is the angle of inclination. An observer would see the earth's surface inclined with this angle of inclination. But this will happen only, if the roundabout rotates with constant angular velocity ω . Then $\vec{K} + \vec{Z}$ is the visual vertical. If there are no strong electric fields nearby, a pendulum moves in this direction, too.

At last we view the loop:

Here we have the gravitational force K and the centrifugal force Z . But the centrifugal force changes all the time. In general the visual vertical is not the direction of $K + Z$. But a pendulum moves in the direction of $K + Z$, if there are no strong electric fields nearby.

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Theory of orientation - The visual vertical", Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2002